

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Distribution ratio of indium-tropolone at pH 4.5 to 8.5

Table a1. The distribution ratio (*D*) at pH 4.5 to 8.5, each value for *D* is an average and standard deviation of three measurements.

pH	<i>D</i>
4.5	4.7 ± 0.4
5.5	4.5 ± 0.5
6.5	4.8 ± 0.5
7.4	4.8 ± 0.5
8.5	2.9 ± 0.2